

The Role of ICT Infrastructure preparedness in Implementation of E-Learning in selected TVET institutions in Nandi County, Kenya

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Abstract

Information communication technology is a tool that is used to communicate, create content, disseminate, store and manage the information for future reference. In technical institutions, ICT infrastructure plays an important role and has effected the implementation of online teaching and learning. The ICT infrastructure is wide and not limited to; number of computer laboratories, internet speed, and poor network coverage and electricity supply. The study was conducted in selected technical training institute in Nandi County. The study sought to determine the Institution's ICT infrastructure preparedness in the technical institution to implement online teaching and learning. A descriptive research design was used in the study; Interview and structured questionnaires, both open-ended and closed, were issued on a sample size of trainees n=475, trainers n=76, ICT technicians n=8 and principals n=5 who were the participants in the five selected technical training institutes in Nandi County. The study revealed that ICT infrastructure was not adequate for smooth online teaching and learning. Local area network and wide area network internet connections in the institutions could not efficiently support online learning. Of the trainers respondents, 14.5% and 46.1% strongly agreed and agreed respectively on LAN and WAN network availability. On reliability of internet in the institution 14.8% and 81% of the trainees reported the internet was reliable and less reliable respectively. Trainee response showed that; 14.8%, 77.4% strongly agreed and agreed respectively on LAN and WAN availability in the institution whereas 42.9% and 57.1% the ICT technicians reported that the internet was reliable and less reliable respectively. Additionally, the institutions' Local area network and wide area network network is limited to the administration office, computer laboratories and institution library only hence restricted coverage. Ensuring ICT infrastructure preparedness is crucial for the smooth functioning of online teaching and learning.

Keywords: eLearning, ICT, Implementation, , Technology. Infrastructure

Introduction

According to UNESCO (2020), more than 1.575 billion students in approximately 188 countries worldwide were affected by the closure of learning institutions due to the preventive measures taken by countries against the spread of COVID-19. World Health Organization recommended that self-isolation, social distancing, and prohibition of persons from assembling in large numbers had been confirmed by researchers as the main measures to combat the spread of COVID-19.

Elearning technology has been considered the most appropriate alternative to keep educational systems functional in many parts of the world during this period (Mbunge et al., 2020). COVID-19 made learning institutions to adopt online learning as education systems need to be abreast with the rapid emergence of new technologies, thus making it a necessity in higher learning institutions in Kenya and the world over.

COVID-19 pandemic affected all countries globally, with most services either stopped or the mode of operation transited from face to face to virtual interfaces. Tamrat and Teferra (2020) stated that shifting to online learning is not a simple task, especially in a continent with only 24% of the total population accessing the internet, where there's poor connectivity, unreasonably high costs, and also frequent power interruptions. Elearning is the learning facilitated and supported with the help of Information and Communications Technology (ICT) through the internet. Unlike the developed world that has increasingly embraced e-learning, this is not the case in Africa.

In Africa, e-learning adoption has been slow because few scholars are familiar with online teaching (Houlden & Veletsianos, 2020). Further, as evidenced in Ugandan higher learning institutions, the absence of internet connection, technical incompetency, and negative attitudes have limited e-learning adoption (Kasse & Balunywa, 2013). Studies have advocated for adequate funds, policy, and infrastructure as the key pillars for e-learning success (Kashorda & Waema, 2014; Bagarukayo & Kalema, 2015).

According to (TVETA, 2020) there was slow implementation of online learning in technical training institute in Kenya due to the lack of an established legal framework and standards to guide a proper roll-out. Most trainees and trainers were challenged with the dynamics surrounding online learning. The technical institutions experienced various challenges during the Covid-19 online learning phases. Therefore, this study aims to determine the infrastructure preparedness among the selected in implementing online teaching and learning in technical institutions in Nandi county Kenya.

Most technical training institutions in Kenya have blended online learning with face-to-face learning and have lagged behind in its full implementation since they are experiencing particular challenges in using the platform (Kashorda & Waema, 2014; Bagarukayo & Kalema, 2015).

Literature review

In this section, we delve into the existing body of literature on E-Learning and Online Learning, with a specific emphasis on the factors influencing the implementation of online learning in technical institutions. The focus of this study is on selected technical training institutions in the North Rift region of Kenya.

E-Learning

Chokri (2012) studied issues contributing to adopting E-learning technology in teaching and learning by students in the university. The study considered the technology acceptance model (TAM) developed by Davis as its reference model (Davis, 1989). Study results showed that the influencing factors of students' positive opinion about the use of E-learning technology could be grouped into three key factors: expertise of learners in ICT technologies for learning, the design of E-learning adopted by lecturers, and the usability of the E-learning platform. The results above show that the study was inclined to variables linked to the Davis model that influenced students' opinions about E-learning technology in teaching and learning. The study did not consider other factors such as ICT infrastructural preparedness, lecturers' ICT skills, and technical skills possessed by ICT staff, which influence the rate of E-learning adoption and affect the continuous user acceptance of E-learning systems.

Al-alak & Alnawas (2011) conducted a study on measuring the adoption of E-Learning by lecturers; to understand their attitudes towards the system. The study adopted Technology Acceptance Model (Davis 1989) as its reference model. This study did not address challenges facing E-learning user acceptance which may be influenced by factors such as ICT infrastructural preparedness and technical skills possessed by ICT staff on E-learning systems after academic staff's acceptance and adoption of E-Learning.

Johnson et al. (2011) researched the adoption of E-learning technologies in the learning process; to identify an innovative way to engage and motivate students in tertiary institutions. The research used case studies and was based on the activity theory framework in all the case studies. Johnson et al. (2011) found out that; 1) E-learning provides learner flexibility but requires careful design and monitoring, 2) E-learning tools can help bridge the gap between students' conceptual thinking and the natural world, and 3) some students do not like using technology as it challenges them to conceptualize new ways of learning. According to Johnson et al. (2011), the design and structuring of E-learning content is a vital component of E-learning system design. Additionally, the issues of technology use pegged to Al-Jaghoub et al. (2009) researched E-Learning adoption in institutions of higher learning in Jordan; to explore changes and challenges Al-Ahliyya Amman University faced in its quest to implement its E-learning program from an information system project point of view.

According to Al-Jaghoub et al., the original E-learning project plan to offer online courses faced issues due to the underlying methodology, which included; 1) Higher education was subject to the laws and regulations of the Ministry of Higher Education (MoHE), which stated that a certain

percentage of any course was to be delivered using traditional teaching methods. 2) Developing an online course proved difficult and time-consuming and lacked key functionalities between students and lecturers. 3) There was a high turnover of human resources, which resulted in changes within the project team. Finally, 4) Technological uncertainty due to the time gap between signing and actual implementation of the project made it necessary to review the original specifications for the IT infrastructure, which seemed obsolete. From the above findings, the study suggests that rolling out practical E-learning projects needs a well-planned plan on several issues to guarantee safe delivery of intended objectives. From the analysis of the findings, the study considered government policies, human resources, availability of technology, and time aspects as the critical factors for the success of the E-learning project.

Russell (2009) studied a framework for managing E-learning acceptance in universities. The study aimed to explore the various methods individual lecturers use in adopting E-learning within their area of specialization work environments, hence developing a framework for analyzing university learning and teaching. From the findings, the study recommended a framework that suggested that a change in the university learning process required coordination across all activities previously handled separately in universities.

ICT infrastructural preparedness

According to Oketch, Njihia & Wausi (2014) and Tarus & Gichoya (2015), ICT infrastructure is insufficient to support ELearning use in Kenya's institutions of higher learning. The concept of ICT infrastructure represents all the technological resources necessary for effective eLearning in institutions of higher learning. Such resources include equipment, media, connectivity devices, and energy sources (Mulwa & Kyalo, 2012). According to Fares (2008), ELearning requires a modern and effective ICT infrastructure that provides reliable high-speed access to wired and wireless networks and the internet. The network infrastructure should support audio, video, and collaborative learning environments.

Mtebe & Mtebe (2014) stated that the cost of acquiring, managing, and maintaining ICT infrastructure had been identified as the major hindrance in the deployment and adoption of eLearning by institutions of higher learning. ICT infrastructure such as the internet, extranet, intranet, and Local Area Networks (LAN) is considered one of the biggest challenges in implementing eLearning in Institutions of higher learning, particularly in developing countries (Fares, 2008). According to Al-adwan & Smedley (2012, p.122), technological obstacles in an ELearning environment often occur in one of three essential components: hardware, software, and bandwidth capacity. Institutions of Higher Learning need to provide wireless and wired networks with high connectivity "bandwidth" to avoid adversely affecting eLearning initiatives (Fares, 2008). According to a survey by Kashorda & Waema (2014) on online learning readiness, universities in Kenya still experience challenges using eLearning technologies. Such difficulties include lack of access to computers, slow internet connectivity, electrical power outages, lack of ICT literacy skills, and inadequate technical ICT technician.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework adopted for this study was E-learning Technology Integration Model, a modified model of the original Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) by Davis (as cited in Shroff, Deneen, and Eugenia, 2011), which was meant to examine students' behavioral intention to use an electronic portfolio system with the aim of understanding how students use and fit it within the specific framework of a course. The study indicated that individual behavior to use electronic systems (for example, e-Portfolio) is driven by behavioral intention, where the behavioral intention is a function of an individual's attitude toward the behavior and subjective norms surrounding the performance of the behavior. Therefore, behavior is a function of both attitudes and beliefs.

The TAM model is chosen due to its solid framework for identifying issues that affect user acceptance of a wide range of end-user computing technologies that provide technical solutions. Shroff, Deneen, and Eugenia, (2011) proposed the TAM to understand and predict the usage and adoption of information technology in a working environment but later was used to study user acceptance of services derived from systems such as E-learning. In TAM, Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use are two main determinants of technology acceptance. Perceived Usefulness is defined as "the degree to which an individual believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her productivity," while Perceived Ease of Use is defined as "the degree an individual believes that using a particular system would be free of effort" (Davis, 1989).

Methodology

The research adopted a descriptive research design to guide the process. The design was used to allow the researcher to collect, summarize, present, and interpret data for clarification. The researcher gathered qualitative and quantitative data. The study was conducted in Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) institutes in Nandi County that are under the Ministry of Education, state department of TVET, offering TVET courses at Higher Diploma, Diploma, Certificate, and Artisan levels.

The study targeted trainers, trainees/students from various departments pursuing different courses, and the principals in different institutions in Nandi county. The institutions were sampled using purposive sampling. According to (Cresswell & Plano Clark, 2011), purposive sampling entails identifying and selecting groups or individuals that are knowledgeable about phenomenon research of interest. The sample size for this study is based on Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size determination formula as cited by Kasomo (2001).

The main data collection tools for this study were questionnaires and interviews. The questionnaire was developed based on the objectives of the study. Five-point-likert scale questions were used and developed based on the study objectives. The researchers administered the questionnaires to the lecturers, the trainees were issued with respective questionnaire and later collected by the research assistant before the end of the day. The researcher designed an

interview schedule to collect information from principals. The study population were trainees (n=4750), trainers (n=380), ICT technicians (n=10) and principals (n=5).

A pilot study was conducted to test the questionnaire reliability and determine the consistency of the scales used to measure the study variables. The pilot study targeted the trainees, trainers ICT technician and principal of the institution. The researcher's supervisors also reviewed the research instruments to ensure there is content validity of the instruments. Cronbach's coefficient alpha, was used to test the internal consistency of data collected. A reliability coefficient of 0.812 ($\alpha = 0.812$) was achieved and was considered reasonable for consistency levels; this meant the instruments were reliable, according to (Dunn, Baguley & Brunsten, 2013), to measure challenges affecting the implementation of online teaching and learning in technical institution.

Data collected were checked and entered into the analysis program IBM SPSS V26. Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and presented using graphs, percentages, and frequency tables. Interview data were analyzed qualitatively by use of content analysis. It was based on an analysis of meanings and the outcome from the respondent information.

On ethical considerations the participants were guaranteed that the disclosed information was kept confidential for its intended purposes. The researcher sought permission from relevant authorities to conduct the research. Informed consent of participants was sought before being involved in the research. The participant anonymity was kept throughout the study and even to the researcher himself to guarantee privacy.

Results

Results covers the analysis of data, its presentation of the major outcomes of the statistical analysis that sought to meet the following objectives; Institution infrastructure preparedness, trainee abilities in online learning, trainee's competence in online teaching and learning, and ICT technician's competence in online learning.

Response rate

The study was conducted in five technical institutions in Nandi County. The overall response rate for this study was 99% (n=473) for trainees, 100% (n=76) for trainers, and 99% (n=7) for ICT technicians overall from all institutions (Figure 4.1). According to authors Mugenda and Mugenda (2009) a response rate of 50% is adequate for analysis and reporting; a rate of 60% is good and a response rate of 70% and over is excellent. Thus, the study response rate was efficient for analysis and reporting.

Fig. 4.1 Response rate for trainers, Trainees, ICT technician and Principals

Demographic information

The study findings revealed that the response for trainers' gender were; male 81.5% (n=62) and female 18.5% (n=14), trainees' gender male 44.4% (n=210) and females 55.6% (n=263) ICT technician respondent were male 85.7% (n=6) and female 14.3% (n=1), whereas the principal gender were male 80% (n=4) and females 20% (n=1) shown in Table 4.2.

Figure 4.2 Gender of the trainees, trainers ICT technicians and Principals.

4.2.1 Respondents age

The age of trainers ranged between 21-25 years 6.6% (n=5), 26-30 years 26.3% (n=20), 31-35 years 51.3% (n=39), 36-40 years 7.9% (n=6), 41-45 years 5.3% (n=4), and 51-55 years 2.7% (n=2). The trainee's respondents age ranged between 16-20 years 16.5% (n=77), 21-25 years 70.8% (n=335), 26-30 years 11.4% (n=54), 31-35 years 0.8% (n=4) and 36-40 years 0.4% (n=0.4%). The ICT technicians aged between 21-25 years 42.8% (n=3), 31-35 years 28.5% (n=2) and 41-45 years 28.7% (n=2), whereas for principals 46-50 years 20% (n=1) and 51-55 years 80% (n=4) (Table 4.4). Mitchell, Clayton, Gower, Barr, and Bright, (2005) reported that there were no gender differences in the levels of adoption of eLearning. Thus, the study

considered the gender distribution as appropriate since it doesn't affect the outcome of the results.

Figure 4.4 Age of Trainers, Trainees, ICT technicians and Principals.

All respondents who participated in this study were confirmed to be bona fide trainees and technician of the sampled institutions. The study respondents showed that most were youths between 16 and 30 years old, which agrees with studies by Bond, Marin, Dolch, et al. (2018) that reported a mean of 24 years. The study sought opinions, attitudes, perceptions, and knowledge from trainees, trainers, and ICT technician and principals to establish Institution ICT infrastructure preparedness in selected technical training institutes in Nandi county..

4.3 Education level of the respondents

From the study education levels of the trainers, 3.9% (n=3), 17.1% (n=13) had PHD and masters respectively. 59.2% (n=45) had bachelor degree whereas 2.6% (n=2) had a diploma (Table 4.6).

. Trainees level of study showed, 10.4 % (n=49) of trainee's respondents were pursuing higher diploma, 70% (n=331) diploma, 18% (n=85) certificate and 1.6% (n=8) artisan courses (Table 4.7). 73.2% (n=346) of the student respondents reported taking technical courses, while 26.6% (n=126) took business courses (Table 4.8).

Trainers' education levels were as follows; Ph.D. (3.9%), Masters (16.9%), Bachelor's degree (58.4%), higher diploma (16.9%), and diploma (3.9%), as shown in Table 4.6 below.

ICT technicians' education levels vary, it ranged from certificate and diploma,. (70%) of the technicians had a diploma and (19%) certificate, as shown in table 4.5.

Table 4.5 Technicians academic qualifications

Education Level for ICT technicians	Frequency	Percent %
PHD	0	0
MASTER'S	0	0
BACHELOR DEGREE	0	0
HIGHER DIPLOMA	0	0
DIPLOMA	5	71.4
CERTIFICATE	2	28.6
TOTAL	7	100

Table 4.6 Trainers academic qualifications

Education Level for trainers	Frequency	Percent %
PHD	3	3.9
MASTER'S	13	17.1
BACHELOR DEGREE	45	59.2
HIGHER DIPLOMA	13	17.1
DIPLOMA	2	2.6
TOTAL	76	100.0

Figure 4.7 Trainees course of study

Figure 4.8 Course category of the trainees

4.6.3 Rate of Access to Computer Laboratories in the institution

The research aimed to establish the rate at which the trainees accessed the computer laboratories weekly for ICT practice use. From trainees responses study revealed, 18.2% (n=86) access the computer laboratory once a week, 12.1% (n=57) access the computer laboratory twice a week, 6.3% (N=30) accessed computers thrice week and 63.4% (N=300) did not have access to computer laboratory. Figure 4.9 shows the frequency of computer laboratory access. The study findings from trainers revealed that 32.9% (n=25) and 10.5% (n=8) of the trainees access computer laboratories once a week and twice a week respectively, 43.4% (n=33) did not have access to computer laboratories (Figure 4.9). The principal from the interview reported that; “Recently there have been increase in number of trainees in the institution and computer available are inadequate for all students”.

Figure 4.9: Figure showing the frequency of Access to Computer Laboratories

This confirmed the inadequacy of computers of computer laboratories in the selected institution. The above study agreed with Kashorda and Waema (2014), who found that the ratio of computers to the student population was comparatively small.

4.6.4 Local area networks and Wide area network availability

The research sought to determine if the technical training institutes in Nandi County were equipped with LAN and WAN internet connections that could efficiently support online teaching and learning. 14.5% (n=11), 46.1% (n=35) strongly agreed and agreed respectively on LAN availability. 23.7% (n=18), 15.7% (n=12) were not sure and disagreed respectively (Table 4.10). The study revealed from trainees response that; 14.8% (n=70), 77.4% (n=366) strongly agreed and agreed respectively on LAN and WAN availability in the institutions. 1.5% (n=7) were not sure, whereas 6.3% (n=30) disagree. Those respondents interviewed also agreed that despite the availability of the local area network, it could not cover the whole institution. The local area network was only limited to the administration, computer laboratories, and library. The institution did not cover a few sections of the library and the rest of the areas.

The findings agreed with Mtebe & Mtebe (2014) that the cost of acquiring, managing, and maintaining ICT infrastructure had been identified as the major hindrance in the deployment and adoption of eLearning by institutions of higher learning. ICT infrastructure such as the internet, extranet, intranet, and Local Area Networks (LAN) is considered one of the biggest challenges in implementing eLearning in Institutions of higher learning, particularly in developing countries (Fares, 2008).

Table 4.10 Table showing Trainers response on local area network availability.

Local area network and Wide area network availability in the institution

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	11	14.5	10.5
	Agree	35	46.1	42.1
	Not Sure	18	23.7	93.4
	Disagree	12	15.7	100
	Total	76	100.0	100.0

Table 4.10 Table showing Trainees response on local area network availability.

Local area network and Wide area network availability in the institution

		Frequency	Percent	Accumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	70	14.8	14.8
	Agree	366	77.4	92.2
	Not Sure	7	1.5	93.7
	Disagree	30	6.3	100
	Total	473	100.0	100.0

From the interview with the principals, the following responses were noted:

"Local area Network and wide area network is available in the institution, but we have restricted to some areas to put the most use where necessary. We have internet in the library for trainees to use, and few computer labs can access the internet at fair internet speed".

"...Local area network and wide area network is available, but we are working on expanding the network within the institution. Currently, we have internet in the administration and library only". "...Local area network is available and currently covers 55% of the institution".

Of the responses, more than 95% had a local area network, but the use was limited. The finding matched the study by Fares (2008) that established that online teaching and learning requires both local and wireless area networks for the internet.

4.6.6 Internet reliability in the institution

The research aimed to establish internet reliability among the selected technical training institutes. The respondent gave out different responses depending on the demographic location of the respective institution. From the study 2.6% (n=2) and 73.7% (n=56) of the trainers reported the internet was reliable and less reliable respectively. 23.7% (n=18) were not sure of the internet reliability (table 4.13). From trainees response the study revealed, 14.8% (n=70) and 81% (n=383) of the trainees reported the internet was reliable and less reliable respectively. 3.8% (n=18) were not sure of the internet reliability (Table 4.14). Furthermore 42.9% (n=3) and 57.1% (n=4) of the ICT technicians reported that the internet was reliable and less reliable respectively (table 4.15).

The presence of free Wi-Fi in institutions enhanced the ability of the trainers and trainees to access the learning materials on the respective platforms. The technical training institutes implemented the eLearning policy by the ministry of education despite the complexity of handling technical courses on online platforms that mainly requires hands-on experience. One principal noted that “... the internet is very slow in the institution, and we have difficulty downloading content”. The results matched the finding (Aboagye et al., 2021) that established the challenge of internet connectivity among college trainees.

Table 4.13 Table showing trainers responses on internet reliability

Internet reliability in the institution.

		Frequency	Percent	Accumulative Percent
Valid	Very reliable	0	0	
	Reliable	2	2.6	2.6
	Not Sure	18	23.7	26.3
	Less reliable	56	73.7	100
	Total	76	100.0	100.0

Table 4.14 Table showing trainees responses on internet reliability

		Frequency	Percent	Accumulative Percent
Valid	Very reliable	2	0.4	
	Reliable	70	14.8	15.2
	Not Sure	18	3.8	19
	Less reliable	383	81	100
	Total	473	100.0	100.0

Table 4.15 Table showing ICT technicians responses on internet reliability

		Frequency	Percent	Accumulative Percent
Valid	Very reliable	0	0	0
	Reliable	3	42.9	42.9
	Not Sure	0	0	0
	Less reliable	4	57.1	100
	Total	7	100.0	100.0

From the technicians responses the study established 28.6% (n=2), 28.6% (n=2) had internet bandwidth of 1-25 megabits per second (Mbps) and 26-55 Mbps respectively. 42.9% (n=3) had 56-75 Mbps (Table 4.16) . From the interview schedule it was reported that only two institutions (25%) had their institutions connected to the fiber optic cable, whereas 87.5% (n=3) of the institutions interviewed accessed their learning management system platform frequently. Other ICT infrastructures recorded in institutions during the study period included blackboard, Moodle, skype, google meet, Zoom, and discord. Communication between trainees, trainers, and ICT technicians occurred mainly on WhatsApp, with lecture notes and assignments sometimes exchanged through email.

Table 4.16 Range of internet bandwidth

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1-25	2	28.6	28.6	28.6
	26-55	2	28.6	28.6	57.1
	56-75	3	42.9	42.9	100.0
	Total	7	100.0	100.0	

The interview sessions conducted with the principal of each institution revealed that most of the institutions sent their ICT technicians for training annually to help them equip themselves with the technological changes and innovations in the market. However, the training frequency varied based on the market demand and the emerging technologies relevant to a particular setting. One ICT technician respondent reported to be frequently trained on ICT technologies. He gave an example of the new Kenya National Examination Council (KNEC) that has online student registration, online result submission, and the milestone of projects and business plans. He further stated that such policies within the technical and vocational training centers warrant frequent training and skills acquisition to meet the institutions' demands.

All respondents agreed to subject their staff to online training as the need arises. For example, the library department has been shifting to allow trainees access self-services; national and international firms trained all librarians and ICT officers within the institutions during the transitional period of indexing all the books, journals, and reports to the systems.

On the other hand, trainees were also trained mainly on how they could use the institution's e-library. ICT technician respondents reported being skilled and knowledgeable on eLearning system resources and were essential in helping the trainers and trainees overcome ICT challenges they would encounter daily. 50% of the ICT technicians attended eLearning workshops at institutions and online platforms to equip their skills and enhance their performances. 75% of the technicians reported being able to track communications between the trainees, trainers, ICT systems and handle bugs that cause errors during learning sessions. 62% of the ICT technicians were knowledgeable and had the technological know-how to protect and encrypt data, thus preventing the institution from online hacking and fraud.

4.7 Challenges of eLearning in technical institutions

The study findings found several challenges hindering the implementation of online learning in selected technical institutions in Nandi county, and they included;

Inadequate ICT infrastructure; the selected technical training institutes are located in rural parts of Nandi county and lack the significant infrastructural development required for an effective and efficient eLearning program. This study finding was in posit with Kibuku, Ochieng & Wausi (2020), who found that Kenya has a rural-urban digital divide regarding ICT infrastructure and

internet connectivity. The urban areas are reported to have more advanced ICT infrastructure and internet connectivity with high speeds ranging from 3G to 5 G, while internet connectivity in rural areas is challenging.

The selected technical training institutions were located in rural areas, which affected the successful delivery of online learning since rural areas have problems with internet connectivity. The rural areas are mainly 3G network coverage zones, while some have poor global mobile communication systems, thus incapable of internet connectivity within the regions. Trainees from home areas who do not have GSM often miss the eLearning sessions, a factor that reduces their performances in their practical and theoretical grading systems. According to the Kenya digital economy blueprint of 2019, about 580 sub-locations in Kenya are below 50% global system for mobile communication, while 160 sub-locations do not have mobile signals. It is evident from this study that some of the areas without mobile signals could be part of Nandi County, where the institutions are located.

The study further reveals that lack of funding has handicapped infrastructure implementation, such as equipping labs with computers and maintaining the LMS network. Poor network connectivity and Internet bandwidth have also hampered quality use. Tarus, Gichoya, and Muumbo (2015) observed that these technological components play a critical role in facilitating accessibility to eLearning by users and should be adequate. There are also reports about a lack of adequate training, policy for developing, using, and securing eLearning, lack of training in LMS and course development, and low motivation for the instructors and administrators. These results are consistent with Kashorda and Waema's (2014) and Bagarukayo and Kalema's (2015) studies, which advocated for funding, policy, and infrastructure as key pillars for eLearning success.

Conclusions

The research raised issues that need attention to successfully implement online teaching and learning in Technical Institutions in Nandi County, Kenya. The study revealed that ICT infrastructure is inadequate for facilitating smooth online teaching and learning. This is due to the low number of computer laboratories, slow internet speed, and poor network coverage. Nandi County Institutions have fewer computers to use in online learning compared to the student ratio. Trainees have less time to use the computer because of the large number of trainees. Additionally, the institutions' LAN network is limited to the laboratories and institution library; hence, some offices outside the administration can't access the LAN internet.

The study also showed that internet speed bandwidths were low, thus rendering it insufficient for all trainees and trainers to use online teaching and learning platforms sufficiently. The network infrastructure by internet providers was well established in the central business district areas which are far from the institution; hence, the institution could not benefit from the fiber optic cable, which can tremendously increase internet speed.

Recommendations

Improve ICT Infrastructure

The institutions in respective technical training institutes needs to improve the internet speed, network coverage, electricity backups, and wireless network coverage. Appropriate infrastructure will enable trainers and trainees to access online learning with ease. With the current increase of learners joining technical training institutes, there is a need to increase eLearning resources for access to learning. The resources for eLearning include computers, laboratories, Local area network coverage, Wide area network, bandwidth connection, etc. The resource should be adequate for the student to use at the appropriate time.

The institution also needs to prioritize the funding of the eLearning section. It allows proper budgetary allocation for eLearning in the institution, thus, its stability. The government should also partner with network providers to provide affordable internet for learners. It reduces the overdependence on the available institutional network. The government also need to provide affordable laptops to trainees. The project on subsidized laptop purchase for university student was initially done in the year 2010 (Wezesha program) that allowed student to purchase laptops at a lower affordable price. It was able to provide a laptop to university trainees at an affordable price. The laptops will reduce computer users within the institution's computer laboratories.

The government should also work with the ministry of education and information communication department to formulate policies that will guide all the institutions to harmonize eLearning across all the institutions. Institution policy will also give trainees a clear understanding of what the trainers expect from them. The institutional policy will guide eLearning activities and give clarity by posting a well-detailed policy document in an important section of the course site. The policy will also assist trainers and trainees since it will make the management of eLearning easy.

References

- Agufana, P. B. (2021). Instructional Usefulness of ICT's as perceived by Lecturers in Technical Training Institutions in Kenya. *International Journal of Education and Research*, **9**, p 87-97.
- Al- Adwan A., Al- Adwan A. & Smedley J. (2013). Exploring students' acceptance of e-learning using Technology Acceptance Model in Jordanian universities, *International Journal of Education and Development using Information and Communication Technology (IJEDICT)*, 9(2), 4-18.
- Al-alak & Alnawas. (2011). Measuring the acceptance and adoption of E-Learning by Academic Staff:A from Jordan University, 17(1), 3–19.
- Alharbi S. & Drew S. (2014). Using the Technology Acceptance Model in Understanding Academics' Behavioural Intention to Use Learning Management Systems, *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 5(1), 1-13.

- Al-Jaghoub S., Al-Yaseen H., Hourani M., Al-Haddadeh R. & Salim M. (2009). E-Learning Adoption in Higher Education in Jordan: Vision, Reality and Change. *European and Mediterranean Conference on Information Systems*, 1-10.
- Bagarukayo, E., & Kalema, B., (2015). Evaluation of e-learning usage in South African universities: A critical review. *The International Journal of Education and Development using Information and Communication Technology*, 11(2), 168-183.
- Chokri B. (2012). Factors Influencing The Adoption of the E-Learning Technology in Teaching and Learning by Students of a University Class, *European Scientific Journal* 8(28), 165-190.
- Cresswell & Plano Clark, 2011),
- Davis, F. D. (1989). *User acceptance of information technology: system characteristics, user perception and behavioral impacts*. University of Michigan, Business School, 38, 475–487.
- Farahat T. (2012). Applying the Technology Acceptance Model to Online Learning in the Egyptian Universities, 64, 95-104.
- Houlden, S., & Veletsianos, G. (2020). Coronavirus pushes universities to switch to online classes – but are they ready?. Retrieved 12th July 2020. The Conversation. <https://theconversation.com/coronaviruspushes-universities-to-switch-toonline-classes-but-are-they-ready-132728> 4.
- Johnson, J. L., Adkins, D., & Chauvin, S. (2020). A review of the quality indicators of rigor in qualitative research. *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education*, 84(1).
- Kashorda, M., & Waema, T. (2014). *E-Readiness survey of Kenyan Universities (2013) report*. Nairobi: Kenya Education Network.
- Kasse, J.,P. & Balunywa, W. (2013). An assessment of e-learning utilization by a section of Ugandan universities: Challenges, success factors and way forward. *In: Paper presented at the International Conference on ICT for Africa 2013*, Harare, Zimbabwe.
- Mbunge, E., Fashoto, S., Akinnuwesi, B., Gurajena, C., & Metfula, A. (2020). Challenges of Social distancing and self-isolation during COVID-19 pandemic in Africa: A *Critical Review*. Available at SSRN 3740202.
- Nagunwa T. & Lwoga E. (2012). Developing E-Learning Technologies to Implement Competency Based Medical Education: Experiences from Muhimbili University of Health and Allied Sciences. *International Journal of Education and Development using Information and Communication Technology*, 8(3), 7-21.

- Namisiko P., Munialo C. & Nyongesa S. (2014). Towards an Optimization Framework for E-Learning in Developing Countries: A Study of Private Universities in Kenya. *Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology* June 2014, 2(2), 131-148.
- Park, S.Y.(2009). An Analysis of the Technology Acceptance Model in Understanding University Students' Behavioural Intention to Use E-learning, *Educational Technology & Society*, 12 (3), 150-162.
- Pirani, J. (2008). Supporting E-learning in higher education. Accessed 7th December 2014 from <http://www.net.educause.edu/ir/library/pdf/ERS0303/ecm0303.pdf>.
- Quadri G.O. (2012). Impact of ICT Skills on the Use of E-Resources by Information Professionals: A Review of Related Literature, *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, ISSN 1522-0222.
- Russell C. (2009). A systemic framework for managing e-learning adoption in campus universities: individual strategies in context, *ALT-J, Research in Learning Technology* 17 (1), 3–19.
- Shroff R. H., Deneen C. C. & Eugenia M. W. (2011). Analysis of the technology acceptance model in examining students' behavioural intention to use an eportfolio system, *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 27(4), 600-618.
- Tamrat, W. & Teferra, D. (2020) COVID-19 poses a serious threat to higher Education. Retrieved 9th Oct 2021 from University world news https://www.universityworldnews.com/page.php?page=UW_Main
- Tarus, J., Gichoya, D., & Muumbo, A. (2015). Challenges of implementing e-learning in Kenya: A study of Kenyan public universities. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*,
- TVET, (2020), Technical and Vocational Education and Training Authority Newsletters. <https://www.tveta.go.ke/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/TVETA-NEWSLETTER-APRIL-2020-min.pdf>. Accessed on 9th Oct, 2021.
- UNESCO. (2020a). COVID-19 Webinar: A new world for teachers, Education's frontline workers. Marrënga Retrieved 11th July 2020 from <https://en.unesco.org/news/covid-19-webinar-new-worldteachers-education-frontline-workers>.
- UNESCO. (2020b). COVID-19 Educational Disruption and Response. <https://en.unesco.org/covid19/educationresponse/225>.